

Tree Index: a new widescale indicator on contribution to mentorship

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Bibliometric indicators have historically focused on counts of publications and received citations as research performance markers. While these provide relevant context into the contribution of researchers, their focus is quite narrow. One of the main missions of academic institutions is training the next generation of researchers. This methodology paper first describes a Tree Algorithm uncovering mentor–mentee links within research mentorship networks using Scopus. It subsequently delves into the construction of a Tree Index measuring the contribution of senior researchers to mentoring the next generation of researchers. Some descriptive results are then presented to illustrate their potential use in exploring the mentorship contribution of senior researchers across countries. These tools also provide unique opportunities to deepen our understanding of the dynamics of research mentorship networks. Such possibilities are introduced in the paper’s discussion.

1. Introduction

Prior studies on mentorship have focused on how mentors affect the career of the junior researchers being trained and mentored (Sorkness, Pfund, & Ofili, 2017) (Ceyhan & Tillotson, 2020). For example, some evidence suggests graduate students with mentors produce more research output than those without, publish more, or receive more grant money (Gingras, Larivière, Macaluso & Robitaille, 2008), and that mentoring can enhance students’ research capabilities and help them identify as researchers (Ferguson & Ellis, 2022). In addition, the research practices and culture established within a mentoring relationship may be propagated by the mentees later in their careers. Other studies demonstrated the importance of mentoring for faculty career development and retention (Miller, Izumi, Denfeld, Rosenkranz & Hansen, 2024).

Like a genealogical tree, a tree model of academic lineage reveals links between generations of researchers. Compared to pre-existing trees such as the Academic Family Tree (<https://www.academictree.org>), which is limited in coverage with 90% of its data coming from US institutions (Schwartz, Liénard & David, 2022), the Tree Algorithm (TA) introduced in this methodological paper enables analyzing the dynamics of research mentorship networks at an unprecedented scale (covering all countries and disciplines) by leveraging the high-quality author profiles of Scopus. Its companion Tree Index (TI) also enables to quantitatively assess how the time and energy senior researchers put towards effective mentorship can create strong effects across subsequent cohorts of scientists.

The TI built on top of the TA also expands the range of available metrics for bibliometric assessments beyond traditional indicators of research performance such as the volume and impact of publications. It enables assessing the contribution of senior researchers (mentors) to mentoring the next generations of researchers looking at the production volume and impact, plus the network size, of their mentees as they go on to independent careers. As such, this indicator captures the lasting contributions senior researchers make to research culture and the research environment through their mentorship practices.

In this paper, we first discuss the methodological choices underlying the TA. We then explain how we validated it using the EThOS database. The approach to derive the TI from the mentor–mentee pairings identified by the TA is then presented along with descriptive results at country level. The paper ends with a discussion of the limitations of the proposed approach and of further research directions. We also identify a potential application of the TA and TI we have been working on to deepen our understanding of the dynamics of research mentorship network.

2. Methodology & Results

With this indicator, researchers are classified as “junior” or “senior” based on their publication history in Scopus, and mentorship links are proxied by specific patterns of publication and co-publication between senior and junior researchers that characterize the mentor–mentee relationship. A composite metric is then computed for each mentee incorporating factors such as the volume and impact of his/her publications, as well as the size of his/her co-authorship network, as he/she goes on to an independent career. These metrics for all an author’s mentees are summed to arrive at the Tree Index (TI) for a mentor. To normalize the metric, the TI is divided by the average TI of all senior authors in the same discipline and career starting year. In the following sections, we present different methodological choices made in designing the indicator.

2.1. Tree Algorithm (TA)

Before computing the Tree Index of a researcher, an algorithm is used to uncover mentor–mentee pairs from the publication records in Scopus. The steps can be summarized as follows. First, senior researchers are identified. A senior researcher is defined as an author still publishing 10 years after the author’s oldest publication in Scopus. The use of a minimum publication age threshold for coding an author as a senior aims at avoiding the inclusion of authors at earlier career stages. Otherwise, most of the linkages would relate to ties between early-career researchers being co-trained. The portfolios of researchers are based on the Scopus AUIDs, which has been shown to be an adequate disambiguated entity for bibliometric purposes (Kawashima & Tomizawa, 2015; Campbell D., Struck B., 2019).

For each junior researcher (potential mentee) appearing in Scopus, potential mentors are identified based on the output of the junior researcher within the first 5 years of his or her publishing career. A mentor is the senior researcher with whom the mentee co-published the largest number of publications during that period. To be assigned to a mentor, mentees must have co-published at least 2 publications with the senior researcher. Also, in case of ties, mentees can be assigned to more than one senior researcher. Additionally, only those mentees who went on to publish at least two publications independently from the mentor are retained, effectively pruning the mentorship tree to those mentees who had a subsequent publishing career.

2.2. Validation of the TA using the EThOS database

To validate the TA, the E-Theses Online Service (EThOS) from the National Library of the United Kingdom was used. EThOS captures the metadata of more than 100,000 theses (mostly for PhDs) awarded between 1980 and 2022 by over 140 UK higher education institutions.

Student and supervisor information (name, affiliation and publication year) were extracted from EThOS to match them to their author identifier (AUID) in Scopus. The matched set was filtered to only retain student-supervisor pairs where both individuals could be matched to an AUID in Scopus. Additionally, to ensure the accuracy of the matched pairs, only those student-supervisor pairs where the matched AUID of the student co-authored at least once with the matched AUID of the supervisor were kept. Using a random sample of 100 such pairs, the accuracy of a matched pair was assessed by comparing the name and affiliation of both the student and supervisor in EThOS with those appearing on their co-published papers. The year(s) of those papers were also compared to that of the corresponding thesis to see if they roughly matched. Overall, 26% of the 147,310 student-supervisor pairs in EThOS were matched with an estimated precision rate of 100%. This resulted in 38,453 matched student-supervisor pairs with at least one co-publication as indexed in Scopus. While recall is low, precision is high. This was an intentional choice as the goal was to later assess the extent to which the TA correctly captures the supervisor of a given student.

Unsurprisingly, the recall of supervisor-student pairs varied across disciplines as defined in EThOS. In some disciplines, mainly in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), supervisor-student pairs are not captured as frequently most likely due to coverage issues in Scopus (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Percentage of captured student-supervisor pairs in EthOS across disciplines.

The thresholds selected in running the TA may also be at play. For instance, publications from the SSH are notoriously less well covered and the research-to-publication lag may be longer such that reaching the 2 co-publications minimum between a mentor and its mentee is likely more difficult in these areas.¹ Even with field normalization, the Tree Index introduced below may disadvantage some SSH researchers due to the above two factors. This is supported by a recall of less than 10% of student–supervisor pairs in the humanities combined with, generally, more than 35% of matched student–supervisor pairs in the humanities having a matched AUID for the student that is not linked to any mentor by the TA; this despite the student and supervisor having co-published at least one paper in Scopus. Accordingly, the Tree Index of a senior researcher may be best presented as an indicator of the mentorship potential for training the next generation of researchers actively publishing in international journals (written in English).

In total, 23% of students among the matched student–supervisor pairs could not be assigned a mentor by the TA. This is likely due to the challenge of matching students to a given senior based on their publication record given the attrition rate of the scientific workforce following the PhD. In short, students often published too few publications to pass the thresholds used by the TA. Disregarding student–supervisor pairs where the TA could not assign a mentor to the student, the share of students linked to the correct mentors equals 77% (ranging from 67% to 83% across disciplines; Figure 2). Unsurprisingly, some of the lowest accuracies were observed in the the SSH.

Figure 2 Percentage of students in EthOS correctly paired across disciplines.

¹ Such thresholds could be modified and tailored to each discipline in the future to optimize the tree algorithm across disciplines.

2.3 Tree Index (TI) Indicator

For each mentee i of a mentor j , three metrics are computed:

- The mentee's publication counts based on publications not co-published with the mentor since their first co-publication (x),
- The sum of the field-weighted citation impact (FWCI) of these documents (y), and
- The number of unique and distinct co-authors of the mentee on these publications (excluding co-authors of the mentor) (w)

The focus on independently authored publications is to measure the contribution of the mentees as they start moving into careers of their own after their training period, without the contribution from their former supervisor. The same logic is applied to the size of their network on these publications which excludes co-authors of the mentor. This last metric aims to capture how the mentees develop and expand their research network outside the realms of their mentor.

The variables x , y and w to be integrated in the below S score for each mentee i have very different scales and their distributions are all characterised by a strong positive skew. To avoid outliers having too much leverage on the resulting S score, as well as to ensure that all three variables contribute roughly equally to S , each variable was log transformed, standardized and re-scaled. Because the distribution of each of the three variables can differ markedly across disciplines and years, the standardization was achieved by converting, for each variable, the value of each mentee relative to the mean and standard deviation of the discipline (D)² and starting year (Y)³ of the corresponding mentor:

$$Z = \frac{v - \mu_{D,Y}}{\sigma_{D,Y}} \quad (1)$$

Where,

- v is the log-value of a given mentee for either of the three variables (x , y , w);
- $\mu_{D,Y}$ and $\sigma_{D,Y}$ are respectively the mean and standard deviation of the corresponding variable (logged) for all mentees, across all mentors, in discipline D and starting year (Y) of the mentor.

The Z scores are then re-scaled so the range of each component is positive and also discipline- and year-specific:

$$Z_{re-scaled} = Z + |MinZ_{D,Y}| \quad (2)$$

Where,

- Z is the standardized score of a given mentee for either of the three variables (x , y , w);
- $|MinZ_{D,Y}|$ is the absolute of the minimum Z score of the corresponding variable for all mentees, across all mentors, in discipline D and year Y .

Using the log-transformed, standardized and re-scaled scores of the three metrics (x , y , w), the composite metric S for a given mentee i is:

² The dominant field of a mentor in Scopus (based on Science-Metrix classification). In case of ties, a mentor is assigned to multiple fields.

³ The publication year of the first paper of a mentor in Scopus.

$$S_i = x + y + w \quad (3)$$

Where,

- x, y, w correspond to the log-transformed, standardized and re-scaled scores as defined in equation 2

The Tree Index (TI) is then computed for mentor j as follows:

$$TI_j = \sum_{i=1}^n S_i \quad (4)$$

Where,

- n equals the number of mentees for a given mentor j .

The resulting TI of a mentor j is then normalized. This is achieved by dividing the TI of a given mentor j in discipline D and starting year Y by the mean TI of all mentors in the corresponding discipline D and year Y :

$$TInorm_{j,D,Y} = \frac{TI_{j,D,Y}}{(\sum_{j=1}^n TI_{j,D,Y}/n)} \quad (5)$$

Where,

- n equals the number of mentors in a given discipline D and year Y .

This normalization is critical to enable aggregation across institutions and countries and ensure the fairness of any resulting comparisons. Indeed, the volume of mentees will vary across disciplines (Figure 3) due to the recall issue noted above as well as will naturally increase with seniority of the mentor. The average TI of all mentors in a given field and career age therefore stands at 1.00. One key advantage of the indicator is that it is quite flexible in its design. For instance, it is possible to weight each of its three components differently depending on the importance users assign to any of them.

Figure 3 Distribution of the number of mentees per mentor across ASJC27 categories.

3. Results — Aggregating TI at the level of countries and institutions

The Tree Index being an author-level metric, it can be aggregated at different levels to generate insights on the outcome of different mentoring practices in different regional/institutional contexts. A use case at national level is depicted below.

Figure 4 presents the performance of countries/regions,⁴ based on the average weighted scores of their institutions. Atop the ranking are Hong Kong and China, which all perform about twice as high as expected based on this indicator.

⁴ Limited to countries with at least 5000 mentors across its institutions.

Figure 4 Average tree index at country/regional level, based on the weighted average of its institutions.

Other top performing nations include Singapore, Pakistan and South Africa, which all appear to have a heavy focus in developing new academic recruits that end up leading successful academic careers. The United Kingdom, driven by some of the top ranked institutions in the World, ranks second among nations with more than 10,000 mentors, at 1.70. Other countries with high mentor population and high mentorship scores include Saudi Arabia (1.70), the Netherlands (1.66), Switzerland (1.63), Malaysia (1.60), Australia (1.57), Germany (1.56), Canada (1.55), Iran (1.54), the United States (1.54), Italy (1.54), Austria (1.53) and Belgium (1.53).

On the opposite end of the spectrum, Ukraine (0.56), Russia (0.83), Argentina (0.84), Poland (0.93) and Mexico (0.98) are among the least performing nations on this new mentorship metric. A clear pattern of lower performance also emerges for nations from Eastern Europe, with more than a dozen countries from the region performing below world level when broadening the analysis. While these findings are not necessarily surprising given that these nations also typically rank lower regarding impact of publications, impact is only a third of the composite, and publication levels and network size are two additional components to the indicator that do not seem to help improve their scoring. Data on mobility tend to demonstrate that individuals from Eastern Europe are less prone to international mobility during their career (European Commission, 2021), which not only has an impact on citation prospects, but also on the broadening of their researcher network beyond that of their mentor.

4. Discussion

We have prepared a novel indicator on mentorship relying on the unique strengths of the Scopus database and its author profiles. The Tree Index can only exist within the context of a database with high-quality disambiguated author profiles, and broad enough coverage to generate analyses on large population sets. Our results demonstrate that the TA is quite accurate and performs strongly in identifying mentor-mentee pairs. Results presented based on the TI currently rely on averages but understanding that skewness plays a role with this indicator, with a low share of individuals presenting with high scores and a long tail presenting with lower scores, other avenues can be taken to aggregate the TI and circumvent this issue, including picking the median or working with percentiles. More work will be performed to better characterize aggregated based on the TI.

Know limitations, in addition to that of author profile splitting and merging that may be more prevalent in some countries than others, include considerations as to how research networks vary across countries. For example, there may exist regions where mentees tend to stay closer

to their mentors. Mentors from such regions would tend to underperform based on the current implementation of the indicator which focuses on new knowledge created independently from the mentor. In countries or disciplines where this coming-of-age scenario is not the norm, TI scores will be lower. We also note that the current approach still quantifies the later “success” of mentees based on traditional bibliometric indicators.

Our definition of mentorship is also up for debate, as shown by results of the validation using EThOS data. While we used these data as a proxy to test how our approach captured mentoring relationships, they do not fully align with how mentorship is defined in our approach. Dependant on use cases, the Tree Algorithm could be modified to better capture the phenomena to be observed. One advantage of our approach is that it can be parameterized to customize it to specific needs, resulting in variants of the Tree Index.

Future work could involve testing variants of the Tree Algorithm and Tree Index to assess whether the signal captured can meet the demand of various consultancy projects. This could involve adjusting the thresholds used by the tree algorithm and the weighting scheme of the Tree Index. Further research could also aim at expanding the range of dimensions captured by the Tree Index components to move beyond traditional measures of research performance.

Perhaps most exciting is the opportunity offered by the Tree Algorithm and Tree Index to deepen our understanding of the dynamics of research mentorship networks. Relying on these new tools, we notably submitted a complementary paper (Campbell, Roberge, & Browning, submitted) exploring the importance of gender role models in research mentorship network.

Open science practices

The new indicator on mentorship developed in this study builds on Scopus, a proprietary data source. Scopus offers disambiguated author profiles, referred to as Scopus author identifiers, of high precision and recall. Their quality remains unparalleled by any other source, whether open or not, and is crucial for an accurate exploration of research mentorship links at-scale. That said, the intent of this publication is to make the approach behind this new indicator as open as possible, accessible for all to review, comment on, and constructively criticize to hopefully inspire further research on the topic of mentorship indicators. using the Scopus database.

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Author contributions

Authors contribution to this work is as follows:

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The authors declare no competing interests.

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